

The Remarkable Spectroscopic and Photometric Variability of T Cha

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Abstract

We report on the ground-based data from a coordinated multiwavelength observing campaign on the highly-variable pre-main sequence star T Cha. The T Cha system is viewed nearly edge-on; much of the variability is likely caused by obscuration by the inner disk. The goal of the campaign is to study the structure of the gas and dust in the inner protoplanetary disk. The campaign was organized around three visits from XMM and the HST, which are reported elsewhere. Here we report on optical spectroscopy and optical and near-IR photometry. The photometry reveals periodicities at either 3.3 or 6.4 days. The color-magnitude diagrams suggest extinction with $A_V > 5$. We took spectra at 10-30 minute time resolution on the 8 nights of the campaign, including a 7.5 hour continuous sequence simultaneous with the third HST/XMM visit. The equivalent width of the $H\alpha$ line varies from -8.5\AA (net emission) to $+2.2\text{\AA}$ (net absorption). We discuss the implications of the photometry and the variability of the $H\alpha$ line profile.

1 Introduction

The classical T Tauri stars in general exhibit a remarkable amount of variability, arising from many physical causes. In February/March 2018 we undertook a week-long coordinated multi-wavelength observing campaign on the violently variable pre-main sequence star T Cha, a $1.5 M_\odot$ member of the ϵ Cha association. T Cha is viewed at an angle of about 70° (Pohl *et al.* 2017); much of the variability is likely caused by obscuration by the inner disk by an irregular disk surface. The primary goal of the campaign is to use the variability to study the structure of the gas and dust in this transition disk.

The campaign was organized around three visits with XMM-Newton and the HST, using STIS and COS for UV spectroscopy, which are reported by Brown *et al.*, elsewhere in this volume. In support, we used the SMARTS Chiron fiber-fed spectrograph to obtain high resolution optical spectra ($R=27,800$; 4080 to 8900Å) and used the SMARTS *Andicam* and LCOGT facilities for optical and near-IR photometry. Here we focus on the OIR photometry and the optical spectroscopy, in particular the extreme variability of the $H\alpha$ line. We confirm many of the characteristics reported by Schisano *et al.* (2009).

2 Observations

The primary ground-based observing campaign began on 2018 February 23 and concluded on 2018 March 1, and was coordinated with three visits to the target by the HST and XMM-Newton. The ground-based high resolution spectroscopy and *ugri* and *BVRIJHK* photometry covered a longer time interval.

2.1 Andicam Photometry

We obtained 24 sets of *BVRIJHK* images with the SMARTS *Andicam* dual-channel imager on the SMARTS/CTIO 1.3m atop Cerro Tololo on the nights of 2018 February 10 through March 2, inclusive. *Andicam* has a $6'$ field of view in the optical, and a $2.4'$ field in the near IR. Three to six dithered images were obtained in each near-IR filter to facilitate sky-subtraction.

Full sets of images were generally obtained nightly, except for 18 February (2 sets with a 1.6 hours spacing) and 1 March (3 sets at about a 2.5 hour cadence). We do differential aperture photometry with respect to about 20 field stars; field stars were flux-calibrated against Landolt standards observed on photometric nights. *JHK* magnitudes were calibrated against 2MASS photometry of the field.

2.2 LCOGT Photometry

We obtained 132 sets of *ugri* images on 35 nights from 2018 February 9 through March 16 using the world-wide LCOGT network. The planned cadence was 1-3 hours. *u*-band images are yet to be calibrated. To facilitate comparison of the datasets we converted the *gri* magnitudes to *BVRI* following the prescription of Chonis & Gaskell (2008).

2.3 Chiron Spectroscopy

Chiron (Tokovinin 2013) is a stable fiber-fed spectrograph at the SMARTS/CTIO 1.5m telescope. It has 4 operating modes; we used it in the lowest resolution mode ($R=27,800$). There is no spatial resolution within the $2''.7$ diameter fiber. The instrument is sensitive from 4080 to 8900Å, in 75 orders, with no interorder gaps shortward of 8350Å. Data reductions are described by Walter (2018).

We obtained 123 spectra in triads of 10 minute exposures, resulting in 41 independent spectra on 19 nights. Five spectra were obtained prior to the formal campaign (18 Jan through 13 Feb), and six spectra were obtained during the week of 11 May 2018. These spectra help us to place the line variability during the campaign in context. Of the spectra obtained during the campaign, 15 triads form a 7.5 hour sequence with about 33 minute effective time resolution simultaneous with the third HST visit.

A typical spectrum is shown in Figure 1. Throughput is calibrated using spectra of μ Col; absolute photometric calibration requires contemporaneous photometry.

Figure 1: The optical spectrum of T Cha on 2018 February 23. The spectrum is that of an early K star photosphere; the only lines in emission are $H\alpha$ and $[O\ I] \lambda\lambda 5577, 6300$; the Ca II triplet lines show central emission reversals, but do not rise above the continuum. The apparent width of the continuum is not noise but rather is due to the photospheric absorption lines seen at $R=27,800$.

3 Photometric Results

We confirm the previously-known result that the star is violently variable (Figure 2), with 2-3 magnitude changes in a day or two. The star gets redder as it gets fainter (Figure 3), as expected for obscuration by cold gas/dust. We use these data to estimate that the ratio of total-to-selective absorption, R_V , is about 5.2 (Figure 4). This indicates that much of the optical and near-IR extinction is due to large grains, as might be expected in the outer parts of an accretion disk. Note, however, that the far-UV extinction (Brown *et al.* 2018) requires a contribution from small grains.

3.1 The Period

We confirm the 3.25 day period in T Cha, first reported by Maunder & Sosna (1975). Periodogram analysis of the optical photometry reveals a very strong periodicity at a period of 3.257 days (false alarm probability $\ll 0.001$) in each of the optical bands (see Figure 5). The near-IR photometry is consistent. The radial velocities (Figure 6) are also consistent with a 3.25 day period, but since half the data were obtained on a single night the significance is by itself not strong.

Since this period is significantly less than expected for a disk-locked T Tauri star (e.g., Edwards *et al.* 1993), we examined whether this period could be half the true period. We subtracted a running 6.5 day mean baseline from the data and redid the period analysis. While the strongest peak in the periodogram remains at 3.26 days, there is significant power at a 6.3 day period (false alarm probability $\ll 0.001$).

Figure 2: All the optical and near-IR photometry. *Andicam* data are solid; LCOGT data are open circles. We have transformed the LCOGT *gri* data to *BVRI* following Chonis & Gaskell (2008). The start and finish times of the HST visits are indicated by the vertical dotted lines. Photometric uncertainties are typically < 0.02 mag, and are not shown.

Figure 3: Color magnitude diagrams from the *Andicam* data. The star becomes redder as it fades (UX Ori-like behavior). The total excursion in V over these 8 nights was 2.5 mag. The cause of the extremely red excursions in $J - K$ when the star is faint is not known. Photometric uncertainties are typically < 0.02 mag (< 0.03 mag on the colors), and are not shown.

The folded light curve still exhibits about 1 mag of internal scatter at each phase, but now exhibits what resembles primary and secondary eclipses or, more likely, occultations by an asymmetrically-warped disk. Both a shortest-string search (e.g., Lafler & Kinman 1965) and a phase-dispersion minimization search (e.g., Stellingwerf 1978) come up with similar periods of 6.5 days, with an estimated uncertainty of ± 0.2 days. The light curve folded on this period is shown in Figure 7.

4 Spectroscopic Results

The only lines consistently seen in emission, aside from $H\alpha$, are $[O\ I] \lambda\lambda 5577, 6300\text{\AA}$. The $[O\ I]$ lines have a constant heliocentric radial velocity of $16 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. We interpret the $[O\ I]$ as arising in a disk wind. The FWHM of $[O\ I] \lambda 6300\text{\AA}$ is 80 km s^{-1} (the line is mildly blended with $\text{Fe I } \lambda 6302.5\text{\AA}$). The correlation between the $H\alpha$ and $[O\ I]$ equivalent widths (Schisano *et al.* 2009) is attributable to the continuum variations. The Ca II IR triplet lines are not in emission above the

Figure 4: The value of the total to selective absorption, $R_\lambda = A_\lambda / E(B - V)$. The points are the measured slope of the appropriate color-magnitude diagram. The magenta and green curves are values of R_λ for $R_V = 3.1$ and 5.2 , respectively. These data support a large value for R_V .

Figure 5: The V magnitudes folded on the best fit period. The blue histogram shows the mean light curve binned in 0.1 phase bins. The labeled phases are arbitrary; minimum radial velocity occurs near photometric maximum.

continuum, but exhibit variable central reversals. $H\beta$ was in emission only on one night, JD 2458174, with an inverse-P Cygni profile. We cross-correlated the $\lambda\lambda 4900 - 5600\text{\AA}$ photospheric spectra to search for changes in the apparent radial velocities. They do indeed show significant variability, with a standard deviation from the mean of 3.4 km s^{-1} and excursions of $\pm 5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Figure 6; also noted by Schisano *et al.* (2009)). At least over a given night (the green points in Figure 6) the variation appear coherent. This could be caused by variable line profiles due to long-lived surface features, or incomplete obscuration of the star by the accretion disk. However, in our limited data set there is no correlation between the stellar radial velocity and the observed magnitude.

$H\alpha$ always appeared in emission above the continuum; during the campaign the equivalent width varied from $+2.2\text{\AA}$ (net absorption) to -8.5\AA (net emission). The $H\alpha$ line flux contributes more to the stellar flux when the star is faint, which indicates that the bulk of the variable $H\alpha$ equivalent width is attributable to the continuum variability (Figure 8). In fact, the wings of the $H\alpha$ emission line do not change ap-

Figure 6: The radial velocities folded on the best fit period. The labeled phases are arbitrary; minimum radial velocity occurs near photometric maximum.

Figure 7: The optical magnitudes folded on a 6.4 day period after removing a 6.5 day running mean. Bands are color-coded. LCO data are indicated by plus symbols; *Andicam* data are filled circles. The phase is arbitrary.

preciably (Figure 9). This suggests that the emission arises in a volume that is largely unaffected by the obscuration of the stellar photosphere by the edge-on disk, or by absorption components along the line of sight.

In addition to the gross changes that are visible in the daily spectra, there are more subtle changes. On the last night of the run we obtained 7.5 hours of nearly-continuous spectra (Figure 10). The data are plotted with 33 minute resolution. Spectra were taken every 11 minutes, so in principle we can study these changes with finer time resolution. The line profile is dominated by the persistent absorption feature at $+100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. A new absorption feature appears in the seventh spectrum at a velocity of -50 km s^{-1} , and grows until the end of the night. On the assumption that the [O I] emission is at rest with respect to the photosphere, this velocity is blueshifted with respect to the stellar photosphere by about 70 km s^{-1} . This may be an outflowing wind stream rotating into our line of sight.

We can estimate the opacity of the $H\alpha$ line. Because the line wings can be fit with a symmetric Gaussian when the absorption is minimal, and because the absolute fluxes of the extended emission wings do not seem to vary, we model the

Figure 8: The flux in the $\lambda\lambda$ 6500-6600Å region as observed (black) and in the interpolated continuum (green) plotted versus the R magnitude. The dotted curve is the expected flux $\propto 10^{-0.4R}$. The $H\alpha$ line contributes less to the total flux when the star is bright, i.e., it is less variable than the continuum. This suggests that the $H\alpha$ emitting region is larger than the stellar photosphere.

underlying emission as a Gaussian. The opacity is then obtained by taking the log of the ratio of the model to the data. This opacity along the line of sight is shown in Figure 11. The strongest feature, at $+100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (heliocentric), is persistent, and may be due to accretion with a rate that varies either with rotational phase, time, or both. The enhanced opacity at -50 km s^{-1} (see Figure 10) also seems to be persistent. There is also evidence of excess emission, at about -150 km s^{-1} and $+250 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, at times. This could be due to spatially extended outflows and high velocity inflows seen off the line of sight to the photosphere.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

The spectra of T Cha show a fairly low activity pre-main sequence star, with a low mass accretion rate. The photometric variability seems to arise largely from obscuration of the photosphere and, to a lesser extent, of the $H\alpha$ emitting region, because it is viewed nearly in the plane of the accretion disk. The surface of the disk may be warped, giving rise to either a 3.3 or 6.4 day periodicity. In addition, the ≈ 1 -1.5 mag scatter in the photometric points at a given phase suggest that the disk surface is not static.

We recover the previously reported 3.3 day period, though it is uncertain whether this is the actual stellar period, due to the length of our observation and the inherent long-term variability of T Cha. The OIR photometry are consistent with a standard extinction law with $R_V > 5$. $H\alpha$ line profiles are consistent with a $H\alpha$ emitting volume much larger than the photosphere. There is persistent $H\alpha$ absorption at about $+100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, likely due to accretion flows, a likely outflow stream at -70 km s^{-1} , and variable higher velocity outflows. There is still much to be done to understand the correlations between the $H\alpha$ line profile and the photometric variability.

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Figure 9: Spectra from each night of the campaign. Where multiple spectra were obtained, only the first is shown. The Julian Date (-2450000) is indicated. Spectra are normalized to the continuum. The least absorption is seen on JD 8174; on that date the line wings are consistent with a symmetric Gaussian profile. Note the persistent absorption at $+90$ to $+100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and variable features at -50 km s^{-1} . The redshifted feature is consistent with absorption in an accretion funnel; blueshifted features likely arise in outflows.

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Figure 10: Spectra from the last night of the campaign. Details are as in Figure 9. Time increases upwards. Each of the 15 spectra is the sum of three 10 minute integrations; this is 7.5 hours of continuous coverage. The effective time resolution is about 33 minutes. Note the appearance and growth of an absorption feature at -50 km s^{-1} starting in the middle of the night.

Figure 11: The $H\alpha$ line opacity, computed assuming a symmetric invariant Gaussian line profile. There is no correction for stellar radial velocity (about $+16 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). The 15 spectra on the last day (Figure 10) are shown in green. The strongest persistent feature is the accretion stream at $+100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The velocity of this varies at the $\pm 10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ level. Variable opacity at negative velocities must be due to outflow. There is marginal evidence for a fast outflow, at about -150 km s^{-1} , in emission.